

REDUCING CARBON FOOTPRINT: STRATEGIES AND METHODS FOR ORGANIZATIONS

¹Maxim Izmaylov, ²Olga Kalinina

^{1,2}Peter the Great St.Petersburg Polytechnic University, Polytechnicheskaya, 29, St. Petersburg,
195251, Russia

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In the context of climate change and growing demands for sustainable development, the implementation of effective strategies to reduce the carbon footprint is becoming an urgent task for business and science. The relevance of this topic is determined not only by the public interest in ecology, but also by the need for organizations to adapt to changing regulatory requirements and consumer expectations. The scientific contribution of this study is the systematization of existing approaches to reducing carbon emissions in organizations, as well as the development of new methods that can be applied in a practical context.

The degree of scientific development of the problem demonstrates that in recent decades the topic of carbon footprint has attracted the attention of researchers from around the world. Many scientific works are devoted to various aspects of carbon accounting, analysis of sustainable development management strategies, as well as the introduction of technologies that contribute to the reduction of equivalent carbon emissions. These works have served as a basis for building a knowledge base and a better understanding of the mechanisms to effectively control and reduce carbon footprint.

The purpose of this study is to identify and analyze the most effective strategies and practices that contribute to the reduction of carbon footprint in organizations, and to assess their impact on sustainable business development. This includes examining various aspects such as energy management, renewable energy use and responsible consumption practices that can significantly affect the overall carbon emission of businesses.

The empirical basis of the study is based on the analysis of company reports, the study of carbon accounting methodologies, as well as on data from practical cases where strategies to reduce carbon footprints have been successfully applied. These sources provide a deeper understanding of how different organizations implement their environmental initiatives and which methods are most effective. For example, by examining the experiences of firms that have implemented renewable energy systems or improved resource management practices, it is possible to gain insight into specific tools and approaches that increase the effectiveness of sustainable initiatives.

The study formulates several key theses that summarize the findings and conclusions. First, optimizing energy management is critical to enabling organizations to significantly reduce their carbon footprint. This can include both technical changes, such as equipment upgrades and the introduction of intelligent management systems, and changes in organizational culture aimed at changing employees' consumption habits. Secondly, the use of renewable energy technologies, such as solar and wind installations, is becoming an important strategic direction to not only reduce CO₂ emissions but also enhance corporate reputation. It has also been found that improving energy efficiency in production processes is directly related to reducing carbon footprints, emphasizing the importance of innovative solutions and investment in new technologies.

Finally, cooperation between organizations, as well as with non-governmental and governmental entities within territorial and global ecosystems, is an important aspect. Sharing best practices and joint initiatives can significantly increase the results in terms of carbon footprint reduction.

The conclusion of the study summarizes the findings and highlights that to achieve effective carbon footprint reduction results, organizations must integrate innovative approaches, improve energy efficiency, and build a sustainable corporate culture. Successful implementation of strategies to reduce carbon emissions not only has a favorable impact on the environmental situation, but also creates a competitive advantage in the market, given the growing interest of consumers in environmentally friendly and sustainable products and services.

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